

MANAGEMENT OF RELATIONS BETWEEN STATE BUDGET REVENUES AND KOSOVO'S GROSS LOCAL PRODUCTION THROUGH QUANTITATIVE ANALYSIS

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Abstract:

The aim of this study is to conduct a quantitative analysis between Kosovo's state budget revenues and Gross Domestic Product (GDP) for the years 2008-2021. I will do this analysis using the simple linear regression econometric model. Then, the mathematical model deals with the relationship and relationship between these macroeconomic quantities through the moment of inertia (gravity) and the coordinates of the centre of gravity of the plane line. In this way, the optimal ratio of these two macroeconomic extents of the Republic of Kosovo has been determined. Determining the optimal ratios helps to establish the balance and consequently the economic development of the country.

Keywords: State budget revenues, Gross Domestic Product, economic development, simple linear regression.

1. Introduction

Economic analysis can determine the interdependence between macroeconomic quantities, the explanation of current movements and their future forecast, the optimal definition and the measures to be taken.

One method for such analyzes could be quantitative methods - whereby applying different mathematical methods the interdependence between macroeconomic quantities is determined. The economic events of the economic system, in which the interdependencies between its variables are presented, form the economic model. Economic models can be mathematical and econometric.

This study will analyze the interdependence between two macroeconomic variables: state budget revenues and Kosovo's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) for the period 2008-2021. This analysis will be done by applying the econometric model of simple linear regression. Quantitative analysis of the ratio of these quantities will then be continued by applying the mathematical model of the moment of inertia and the coordinates of the center of gravity in the coordinate system perpendicular to the plane line. Thus, quantitative analysis determines the optimal solution to the interdependence of these two macroeconomic quantities. This optimal solution ensures a balance that contributes to the economic development of the country.

2. Methodology of formulating of the econometric and mathematical model

2.1. Simple linear regression

The simple linear regression model is one of the econometric models that can be represented by the equation:

$$y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_i + \varepsilon_i, \quad 0 < \beta_1 < 1 \quad (1)$$

This model is linear, has an independent variable x that has an impact on the variable y and is stochastic which means that there is no exact connection between the variable x and that y but it also has the stochastic element ε .

After determining the model we need to do the model evaluation. Since equation (1) must be evaluated it takes the form:

$$\hat{y}_i = b_0 + b_1 x_i + e_i \quad (2)$$

The parameters should be evaluated b_0 and b_1 . The appearance of the function depends on the parameter values. The parameter b_0 sets the intersection to the ordinate, and b_1 sets the angle or direction of the function. The setting of the parameters is done in such a way that we minimize the sum of all deviations, that is $\min \sum e_i$, but in order to avoid the possibility of eliminating the sum of all deviations, it must be raised to the square. Using the method of small squares based on the criterion of minimizing the square of the deviation we can define it as:

$$\min \sum_{i=1}^n e_i^2 = \min \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - b_0 - b_1 x_i)^2 \quad (3)$$

By partially deriving equation (3) according to the parameters b_0 and b_1 , then we equate the obtained equations with zero and after the necessary adjustments we get the following coefficients:

$$b_1 = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \tilde{x}_i \tilde{y}_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n \tilde{x}_i^2} \quad (4)$$

$$b_0 = \bar{y} - b_1 \bar{x} \quad (5)$$

Where $\bar{x}$ and $\bar{y}$ represent the middle of the sample, and $\tilde{x}$ and $\tilde{y}$ represent the variables x and y their form of deviation:

$$\tilde{x}_i = x_i - \bar{x}, \quad \tilde{y}_i = y_i - \bar{y}$$

By using equations (4) and (5), we can obtain the parameters of the model based on the method of squared square in the case of an independent variable.

2.2. Coefficient of elasticity (Elasticity of economic functions)

Determining how the change of one economic variable affects the change of the other variable, which is related to it, is one of the important problems in economics. This measurement is made with the help of the coefficient of elasticity $E_{y,x}$, where x it is an independent variable, while y it is a dependent variable.

Let x and y be both economic quantities and let be $y = f(x)$, where f is the derivative function.

The coefficient of elasticity is $E_{y,x} = \frac{x}{y} \cdot \frac{dy}{dx}$.¹ (6)

For the function $y = f(x)$ we say is the unit resilient to changes from x if it is $|E_{y,x}| = 1$, respectively $E_{y,x} = -1$ (7)

or $E_{y,x} = 1$.¹ In this case, the percentage change of the variable y is equal to the percentage change of the variable x .

2.3. The differential of the arc and the length of the arc line in the plane

Let the curve be given $y = f(x)$ and at it point A with the abscissa $x = a$. Let M be the moving point of the curve with the abscissa x . As x it changes, so does the position of point M . The length of the arc of the curve from point A to point M we mark with s . If we fill the figure with other elements as in the picture.¹

Figure1. Arc Differential

Figure 1: Arc Differential,

Based on figure 1 we find that: $\lim_{\Delta x \rightarrow 0} \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{\Delta y}{\Delta x}\right)^2} = \sqrt{1 + y'^2}$

$\lim_{\Delta x \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta s}{\Delta x} = s'(x)$

$$\lim_{\Delta x \rightarrow 0} \left(\sqrt{1+y'^2} + \frac{\Delta y}{\Delta x} - y' \right) = \sqrt{1+y'^2} + y' - y' = \sqrt{1+y'^2}$$

After the necessary adjustments it follows that $s'(x) = \sqrt{1+y'^2}$. We can also write this result in the form $\frac{ds}{dx} = \sqrt{1+y'^2}$ or $ds = \sqrt{1+y'^2} dx$ (8)

Equation (8) can also be written in the form:

$$ds^2 = \left[1 + \left(\frac{dy}{dx} \right)^2 \right] dx^2 \quad (9)$$

It means $ds^2 = dx^2 + dy^2$. Size ds is the differential of the arc.

2.4. Length of the line arc in the plane

Let the curve be given $y = f(x)$ at both points A and B with the abscissa $x = a$ and $x = b$. M let it be an arbitrary point in the arc AB , with the abscissa x . The length of the arc AM is a function of x : $s = s(x)$. If $x = a$ then $s = 0$, means $s(a) = 0$.

Figure 2. The length of the line arc in the plane

Source: Length of the line arc in the plane

According to equation (8) the derivative of the function $s(x)$ was: $s'(x) = \sqrt{1+y'^2}$

If equation (8) is integrated, the length of the curve arc $y = f(x)$ from the point $x = a$ to the point $x = b$ given by the equation is obtained:

$$s = \int_a^b \sqrt{1+y'^2} dx \quad (10)$$

2.5. Moments of inertia and coordinates of the center of enormity (gravity) of the arc of a line in the plane

For the line given in the plane given by the equation $y = f(x)$, the length of the arc is

$$s = \int_a^b \sqrt{1+y'^2} dx,$$

and the moment of inertia to the axis ox is¹

$$I_x = \int_s y ds = \int_a^b y \sqrt{1+y'^2} dx, \quad (11)$$

while the moment of inertia about the axis oy is

$$I_y = \int_s x ds = \int_a^b x \sqrt{1+y'^2} dx. \quad (12)$$

The coordinates² of the center of gravity::

$$x_t = \frac{I_y}{s}; \quad y_t = \frac{I_x}{s}, \quad (13)$$

that after the substitutions of I_x and I_y we obtain:

$$x_t = \frac{\int_a^b x \sqrt{1+y'^2} dx}{\int_a^b \sqrt{1+y'^2} dx} \quad \text{respectively} \quad y_t = \frac{\int_a^b y \sqrt{1+y'^2} dx}{\int_a^b \sqrt{1+y'^2} dx} \quad (14)$$

3. Data

In the following table presented are the movements of the state budget revenues of the Republic of Kosovo and GDP for the period from 2008 to 2021.

Table1. Processing of data received in millions of euros (in 000)

Year	GDP	Revenue	Participation of state budget revenues in GDP	Base Index 2008 = 100 of revenue share in GDP	Base Index 2008 = 100 of BPV	Base Index 2008 =100 of the budget revenues
2008	3,537	932	26.35	100	100	100
2009	3,610	1,145	31.72	120.37	102.06	122.85
2010	4,030	1,127	27.97	106.13	113.94	120.9
2011	4,555	1,279	28.09	106.59	128.75	137.23
2012	4,797	1,284	26.77	106.58	135.62	137.77
2013	5,071	1,316	25.95	98.49	143.37	141.20
Budget	100	1,334	26.05	95.07	150.55	143.13
2015	5,674	1,458	25.70	97.52	160.42	156.44
2016	6,037	1,777	29.40	111.71	170.68	190.67
2017	6,356	1,923	30.25	114.82	179.70	206.33
2018	6,671	2,009	30.12	114.29	20186	215
_	_	75222	199.49	119.51	238.41	6,771
2020	32.58	2,206	123.64	191.43	236.70	8,091
2021	95.83	2,043	25.25	228.75	219.21	Source

Processing of data by the author obtained from the Kosovo Agency of Statistics and Annual Financial Reports of the Kosovo Government. For 2021, data have been obtained evaluated.

From the table above it can be seen that, for the analyzed period, GDP has increased by 128.75%, while the state budget revenues by 119.21%. Significant increase of state budget revenues was made in 2016 by 34.23% compared to 2015. In 2021, the basic index of growth of state budget revenues is 219.21, while GDP for the same year is 228.75.

4. Research results

In the formulated model, the role of the independent variable is taken by GDP, which is a function of state budget revenues.

Thus: Budget revenue = f (GDP)

Based on equation (2): $y_i = b_0 + b_1x_i + e_i$

x_i - GDP,

y_i - State budget revenues

To determine the parameters $b_0 = \bar{y} - b_1\bar{x}$ and $b_1 = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \tilde{x}_i \tilde{y}_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n \tilde{x}_i^2}$, where $\bar{x}$ and $\bar{y}$ the middle of the

sample, and $\tilde{x}$ and $\tilde{y}$ note the deviations for x and y respectively. So, $\tilde{x}_i = x_i - \bar{x}$, $\tilde{y}_i = y_i - \bar{y}$ we do the necessary calculations.

In the following table we calculate the values of the parameters based on the method of the squared squares of the deviation:

	y_i	x_i	$\tilde{y}_i$	$\tilde{x}_i$	$\tilde{x}_i \tilde{y}_i$	$\tilde{x}_i^2$	$\hat{y}_i$	e_i	e_i^2
	932	3,537	-643.36	-2,004.	1,289,563	4,017,733	975.26	-43.26	1,871.11
	1,145	3,610	-430.36	-1,931	831,204	3,730,416	997.11	147.89	21,870.98
	1,127	4,030	-448.36	-1,511	677,659	2,284,416	1,122.85	4.15	17.19
	1,279	4,554	-296.36	-987	292,631	975,015	1,279.73	-0.73	0.54
	1,284	4,797	-291.36	-744	216,894	594,173	1,352.48	-68.48	4,690.13
	1,316	5,071	-259.36	-470	122,009	221,303	1,434.52	-118.52	14,046.21
	1,334	5,325	-241.36	-216	52,236	46,841	1,510.56	-176.56	31,173.83
	1,458	5,674	-- 117.36	132	-15,558	17,575	1,615.05	-157.05	24,663.88
	1,777	6,037	201.64	495	99,928	245,591	1,723.73	53.27	2,838.22
	1,923	6,356	347.64	814	283,179	663,526	1,819.,23	103.77	10,768.29
	2,009	6,671	433.64	1,129	489,830	1,275,931	1,913.54	95.46	9,113.24
	2,222	7,056	646.64	1,514	979,386	2,293,926	2,028.80	193.20	37,325.90
	2,206	6,771	630.64	1,299	775,420	1,511,845	1,943.48	262.52	68,919.14
	2,043	8,091	467.64	2,549	1,192,288	6,500,314	2,338.67	-295/67	87,418.94
Amount	22,055	77,580	0.00	0.00	7,286,675	24,338,611	22,055	0.00	314,717
Mesi	1,575.36	5,541.43					1,575.36		22,479

$$b_1 = 0.299387, b_0 = -83.68$$

Obtained values of b_0 and b_1 we substitutes in equation (2) to find $\hat{y}_i$, for the period under analysis 2008 - 2021. In other words, the sample regression line is $\hat{y}_i = -83.68 + 0.299387 \cdot x_i$.

This equation represents the estimated regression equation that approximates the relationship between the size of state budget revenues and GDP.

To determine how well this estimated equation approximates the data we show it with the coefficient of determinability.

From the table we see that $SKG = \sum e_i^2 = \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2 = 314,417.60$, which measures the error made when we use the estimated regression equation to predict state budget revenues.

To measure how much the values of $\hat{y}$ the estimated regression equation deviate from $\bar{y}$, one must calculate another sum of squares called the sum of the squares due to the regression¹:

$$SKR = \sum_{i=1}^n (\hat{y}_i - \bar{y})^2 = 2,181,539.62$$

While the total sum of the squares is: $SPK = \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2 = 2,496,257.21$

Since $SPK = SKR + SKG$ then, in a perfect approximation, $SKP = 0$ and $SKR = SPK$ where their ratio would be $^2 \frac{SKR}{SPK} = 1$ ∴

The ratio $\frac{SKR}{SPK}$ is the coefficient of determinability, and is denoted by R^2 , therefore:

$$R^2 = \frac{SKR}{SPK} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (\hat{y}_i - \bar{y})^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2} = 0.873924211 \text{ expressed as a percentage this coefficient can be}$$

interpreted as the percentage of the total sum of squares that can be explained using the estimated regression equation. In other words 87.39% can be explained by the linear relationship between state budget revenues and GDP.

In the following we will look at the correlation coefficient to show the degree of hardness between the two variables, in our case the state budget revenues and GDP. The values of the correlation coefficient are always between -1 and $+1$. A value as close as 1 indicates that the variables have a perfect linear relationship.

$$R = \sqrt{R^2} = \sqrt{0.873924211} = 0.934839136$$

With the coefficient $+ 0.934839136$, we can conclude a strong positive correlation between state budget revenues and GDP.

Whereas, the coefficient b_0 represents the level of state budget revenues that will be when the level of GDP would be equal to zero. The coefficient b_1 indicates how much the level of state budget revenues would increase when the level of GDP would increase per unit. From the calculations made, the following relation is obtained:

$$T\ddot{e} \text{ ardhurat e buxhetit t\ddot{e} shtetit} = -83.68 + 0.299387 \cdot BPV$$

In the following study to make the quantitative analysis between the state budget revenues and GDP, the mathematical model is applied as described in the formulation methodology.

For this reason the regression function is used

$$y = -83.68 + 0.299387 \cdot x$$

To limit the share of state budget revenues in GDP, the integration boundary is set based on the coefficient of elasticity:

$$E_{y,x} = -1$$

$$E_{y,x} = \frac{x}{y} \times \frac{dy}{dx}$$

$$\frac{x}{y} \times \frac{dy}{dx} = -1$$

From the regression function $y = -83.68 + 0.299387x$ we find $\frac{dy}{dx} = 0.299387$ from $x = 139.75$ this means that the movement of GDP from 0 to 139.75 mil. €, the elasticity is less than 1.

Now we determine the length of the arc s of the plane line from equation (10),

$$s = \int_0^{139.75} \sqrt{1 + 0.08963} dx = \sqrt{1.08963} \int_0^{139.75} x dx = 145.88$$

In the following we find the moments of inertia and the coordinates of the centre of gravity of the plane line.

Based on formulas (11) and (12) we find the moments of inertia (gravity) I_x and I_y .

$$I_x = \sqrt{1.0676} \times \int_0^{139.75} y dx = 1.033 \times \int_0^{139.75} (-83.68 + 0.299387x) dx =$$

$$= 1.04385 \times (-83.68 \times (139.75 - 0) + 0.299387 \times (9,765,03 - 0)) =$$

$$= 1.04385 \times (-11,694.28 + 2,923.52) = 1.04385 \times (-8,770.76) = -9,155.36$$

$$I_y = \sqrt{1.04385} \times \int_0^{139.75} x dx = 1.04385 \times (9,765.03 - 0) = 10,193.23$$

While based on formulas (14) we find the coordinates of the centre of gravity:

$$x_t = \frac{10,193.23}{145.88} = 69.87$$

$$y_t = -\frac{9,155.36}{145.88} = -62.76$$

Thus, using linear regression and the mathematical model, quantitatively, the optimal size y_t of the state budget revenues, x_t which represents GDP, has been determined.

From here we can conclude that the state budget revenues will have to be reduced for the analyzed period by 62.76 mil. €, while at the same time GDP should be increased by 69.87 mil. €.

5. Conclusions

In this study, through simple linear regression and mathematical model, the ratio of macroeconomic quantities, state budget revenues and GDP of the Republic of Kosovo was analyzed. Through such models, functional links can be established between macroeconomic quantities that help the economic development of the country. The role of mathematical and econometric models increases especially when it is necessary to influence the development of the country through fiscal policies and find optimal solutions. Such analyzes help especially when the share of state budget revenues in GDP should be limited, especially when fiscal policies should affect the economic development of the country. Quantitative analysis has determined less state budget revenues by € 62.76 million, while on the other hand GDP increase by 69.87 mil. €.

According to these results, we conclude that the relations between these macroeconomic quantities must be in a balance for an economic development of the Republic of Kosovo, otherwise it may lead to a further decline in GDP.

Conflict of Interest

The authors confirm that there is no conflict of interest to declare for this publication.

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